

Developments in the Field of Cardiac Surgery

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Abstract: *This article provides information about the importance of cardiac surgery in the modern world. Just as this field has changed since its inception, the use of modern technologies has facilitated the work of doctors.*

Keywords: *Cardiac surgery, heart, vessel, cardiovascular system, anesthesia, blood circulation, ischemic disease, valves, heart threshold.*

Date of Submission: 20-10-2024

Date of Acceptance: 14-11-2024

Cardiac surgery is a field of medicine that deals with the surgical treatment of diseases of the heart and large vessels. This specialty is one of the most complex and high-tech in modern medicine, as it requires deep knowledge and skills to work with the most important human organ. Cardiac surgeons perform operations that can save the lives of patients with severe cardiovascular diseases, and therefore their work requires the highest qualifications, precision and responsibility.

History of cardiac surgery

The development of cardiac surgery began relatively recently. The pioneer in this field is considered to be the German surgeon Ludwig Reichenbach, who in 1896 successfully removed a knife wound from a patient's heart. However, cardiac surgery really began to develop only in the middle of the 20th century thanks to advances in anesthesiology, antibacterial therapy and artificial blood circulation technologies.

One of the key events in the history of cardiac surgery was the discovery of the artificial blood circulation machine, which made it possible to temporarily replace the functions of the heart and lungs during surgery. The device was first used in 1953 and revolutionized heart surgery by allowing complex open-heart surgeries to be performed.

Main areas of cardiac surgery

Modern cardiac surgery includes several main areas, each of which requires specific knowledge and skills. Here are the main ones:

- **Coronary artery bypass grafting.** This is an operation in which an additional path for blood flow is created, bypassing blocked coronary arteries. Coronary artery bypass grafting is one of the most effective ways to treat coronary heart disease.

- Replacement and reconstruction of heart valves. This operation is performed when the valves that regulate blood flow in the heart are malfunctioning. In some cases, the valves can be restored, and in other cases, they require complete replacement.
- Correction of congenital heart defects. Congenital heart defects are structural abnormalities that develop in a child before birth. Modern technologies make it possible to successfully treat most congenital heart defects, improving the quality of life of patients.
- Heart transplantation. In the case of severe heart disease, when other treatments no longer help, the only way out may be transplantation. This is a complex and expensive procedure that requires the coordinated work of many specialists.

Indications for cardiac surgery

Cardiac surgery is indicated for the following conditions:

- Coronary artery disease, accompanied by angina and heart attacks.
- Congenital heart defects, such as atrial or ventricular septal defects.
- Heart valve problems, such as stenosis or insufficiency.
- Severe heart failure that does not respond to drug treatment.

The decision to perform surgery is made after a thorough examination of the patient and a discussion of possible risks and complications. Cardiac surgeons use modern diagnostic techniques, such as echocardiography, angiography, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), to accurately determine the condition of the heart and plan the operation.

The course of cardiac surgery

Cardiac surgery usually requires general anesthesia and connection of the patient to a heart-lung machine. This device temporarily takes over the functions of the heart and lungs, providing the body with oxygen and removing carbon dioxide. During the operation, the heart can be stopped, which allows the surgeon to perform manipulations safely. After the main stage of the operation, the patient's heart is restarted and blood circulation is restored. The operation can last from several hours to half a day, depending on its complexity.

Postoperative period and rehabilitation

After cardiac surgery, the patient is transferred to the intensive care unit, where he is under 24-hour supervision of medical personnel.

The first days after surgery are the most critical, as complications such as bleeding, infections, or heart problems may occur.

Rehabilitation after cardiac surgery includes a set of measures aimed at restoring physical activity, normalizing the cardiovascular system, and improving quality of life. The rehabilitation program may include exercise therapy, physical therapy, diet therapy, and psychotherapy. Patients are advised to follow a diet that excludes foods high in fat and cholesterol, control their weight, exercise, and avoid stress.

Risks and complications of cardiac surgery

Cardiac surgery is associated with certain risks, despite its high success rate. Complications include:

- Bleeding and hematomas.
- Infectious complications.
- Thromboembolic complications, such as stroke.
- Heart rhythm disturbances, such as arrhythmia.
- Damage to other organs and tissues.

Cardiac surgeons take all possible measures to minimize risks. Modern technologies, such as robotic surgery and minimally invasive techniques, also help reduce the trauma of operations and speed up patient recovery.

Modern technologies in cardiac surgery

Modern technologies and innovations play a key role in the development of cardiac surgery, making operations safer, more effective and accessible. The introduction of robotic surgery, minimally invasive techniques, advanced imaging technologies, as well as research into the possibilities of gene therapy and regenerative medicine - all this has significantly expanded the possibilities of treating cardiovascular diseases. Let's look at the main technologies that are actively used today and open up new horizons in cardiac surgery.

Minimally invasive surgery

Minimally invasive cardiac surgery (MIC) is a technique in which surgeons perform operations through small incisions (up to 5-6 cm in size) instead of the traditional chest incision. This approach significantly reduces the trauma of the procedure, reduces the risk of infectious complications and speeds up the patient's recovery.

Some of the main types of minimally invasive procedures include:

- Minimally invasive coronary artery bypass grafting — creating bypasses for blood around blocked arteries.
- Transcatheter valve replacement — a procedure in which a new heart valve is inserted through a catheter without making any incisions in the chest.
- Endoscopic surgery — using small cameras and instruments to perform heart surgery through small openings.

The benefits of minimally invasive surgery include a shorter hospital stay, less post-operative pain, and a quicker recovery from surgery.

Robotic Surgery

Robotic systems allow the surgeon to perform surgery with great precision and minimal incisions. One of the most popular systems is the da Vinci robot, which provides the surgeon with improved visualization and allows him to manipulate instruments with greater flexibility and precision. With robotic systems, surgeons can perform more complex surgeries on heart valves, coronary vessels, and even repair congenital heart defects.

The benefits of robotic surgery include:

- Reduced risk of damage to surrounding tissue.
- Reduced errors due to improved accuracy.
- Shorter recovery time for the patient.
- The ability for surgeons to perform procedures remotely, which is especially important in remote areas.

Imaging technologies

Modern imaging techniques such as three-dimensional echocardiography (3D ECHO) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) play a key role in diagnosis and preoperative planning. These technologies allow cardiac surgeons to obtain a detailed image of the heart and large vessels, which facilitates accurate planning and performance of operations.

- Three-dimensional echocardiography. This method provides the ability to obtain three-dimensional images of the heart in real time, which allows you to see the structural features of the organ and evaluate the functioning of the valves.
- Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). MRI is an indispensable method for complex heart surgeries, as it allows you to obtain high-quality images of tissues and blood vessels without the need for contrast agent.
- CT coronary angiography. CT scans using contrast can detect coronary artery disease and assess the degree of narrowing. These imaging techniques not only improve diagnostics, but also minimize the risk of complications because surgeons can more accurately see and understand the anatomy of each patient's heart.

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning are beginning to be actively implemented in cardiac surgery to analyze medical data, diagnose and predict surgical outcomes. AI is capable of analyzing a huge amount of patient data, helping surgeons make decisions more accurately and quickly.

- Patient data analysis. AI-based systems can identify patterns in data, which helps predict the development of diseases and select individual treatment methods.

Prospects for the development of cardiac surgery

The future of cardiac surgery is closely linked to a number of promising areas that promise to further improve the quality of treatment and reduce risks. Let's consider the main ones:

- Cell and tissue engineering. Research in the field of regenerative medicine is aimed at creating cardiac tissue from stem cells that could replace damaged areas of the heart. In the future, this may become an alternative to transplantation and allow the restoration of cardiac tissue in case of damage and disease.
- Gene therapy. The possibility of treating genetic heart diseases with the help of genetic modification opens up new prospects for patients with congenital pathologies. Gene therapy can reduce the risk of developing heart disease and help combat chronic heart disease.

- Development of an artificial heart. Today, there are devices that can temporarily replace heart function in patients awaiting transplantation. However, the goal of scientists and engineers is to create a fully autonomous artificial heart, which could become a long-term alternative to transplantation.
- Robotic and remote surgeries. Remote control systems for surgical robots allow experienced specialists to perform operations at a distance. This is especially important for remote regions where there is no access to qualified cardiac surgeons.
- Artificial intelligence and machine learning. These technologies are already being used to analyze medical data and help doctors make diagnoses faster and more accurately. In cardiac surgery, AI can help in preoperative planning and predicting the outcome of operations, which will reduce the number of complications and improve treatment results.

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Conclusion

Modern research in the field of cardiac surgery allows us to study diseases early. With the help of technology and artificial intelligence, we can prevent the development of the disease and death. This will help doctors, as well as patients, increase the percentage of successful treatment.

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